

Renewable Energy in Bristol: Opportunities and challenges in the post subsidy landscape

Kick off workshop

Tuesday 11 June 2019, 17:30-20:00

Engine Shed, Station Approach, Temple Meads,

Bristol, BS1 6QH

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About PROSEU:

PROSEU is an EU-funded research project, bringing together the University of Leeds, Bristol Energy and Bristol Energy Cooperative as well as eleven project partners from seven European countries (Universities, research institutes and consultancies, non-governmental and non-profit organisations). It aims to enable the mainstreaming of the Renewable Energy System (RES) Prosumer phenomenon across Europe, through a range of skillsets including: Business model and financing experts; legal and regulatory specialists; energy engineering and policy expertise.

PROSEU Project Partners

About PROSEU European Living Labs:

The concept of Living Labs is being applied across Europe to support innovation in a wide range of sectors. This experimental approach is based on the collaboration of a large panel of stakeholders in face-to-face settings. PROSEU is establishing RES Living Labs to engage with renewable energy stakeholders from government, the business sector and civil society. This process recognises that the challenges that have been addressed and the solutions that have been developed by each Living Lab will differ depending on the local context. At the Living Labs all stakeholders have an equal opportunity to participate.

PROSEU will apply this approach in its research, by setting up at least 15 RES Living Labs in 9 countries across Europe. The RES Living Labs are based on the highly participatory method of “co-creation” –a way to bring citizens to the front and centre. Through these Living Labs, citizens will contribute to promoting a more sustainable, democratic and inclusive energy transition.

The [PROSEU research team](#), drawing on the collective experience of the stakeholders involved, will facilitate several co-creation sessions, capturing the different contexts and challenges in operational roadmaps. Alongside the Bristol our Portuguese RES Living Lab, involves representatives of [wineries from the Alentejo region](#) who are dedicated to adopting renewable energy production and self-consumption. Other Living labs will be held with the municipality of Santorso in Italy, with Somenergia in Spain as well as in The Netherlands.

PROSEU aims to build links between these living labs through [a community of interest](#) network and a series of conference style events, where participants from the different living labs will have the opportunity to meet one another and share experiences.

For more information about PROSEU's approach and on participating in Living Labs, you can check out [this article on our website](#). For the Living labs we are working with, you can visit [this page](#).

Join us in helping make the renewable transition a reality!

Bristol Living Lab Partners

About the Event:

Energy systems are undergoing significant change. Traditional centralised, fossil-based systems are giving way to increasingly low carbon, renewable and decentralised energy systems. Whilst these changes aim to reduce CO₂ emissions, this has also enabled the emerging 'prosumer' phenomenon: where citizens and businesses play an active and democratic role in the generation, ownership and direction of energy transitions. In recent years this seen an explosion in community, municipal and business involvement in Bristol.

However, the UK's Feed-In-Tariff (FIT) closed to new applicants from 1st April 2019. Although the cost of renewables has fallen sharply in recent years, this post subsidy landscape presents serious challenges for Bristol's nascent decentralised energy scene.

In this first in a series of events, we set out to explore the challenges and opportunities facing the Bristol energy scene in a post subsidy landscape. As part of PROSEU project we will offer a series of free 'Living Lab' practical interventions/workshops to see how Bristol can continue to be a frontrunner city in the UK's energy transition. In this event we aimed to bring together a diversity of actors including local government, community energy organisations, businesses, citizens, academia and the third sector.

The three hour event involved a series of plenary presentations from Bristol Energy Company, Bristol Energy Cooperative and academics from the University of Leeds. Subsequently, discussion focussed on four key themes, seen to be crucial in getting new projects off the ground in a post subsidy landscape:

- **Project Pipeline**
- **Business models**
- **Financing**
- **Regulation**

The following document sets out the findings from the workshop as well as some future options for the Bristol Living Lab.

Project pipeline

'Bristol has the lowest carbon footprint of any of the UK's Core Cities, was the UK's first European Green Capital in 2015, has possibly the largest environmental network of its kind in Bristol Green Capital Partnership, won the 2018 GLOMO Smart City Award, was voted the number one smart city in the UK in 2017, successfully delivered c£50m of low carbon energy investment between 2012 and 2016 and set up one of the only municipally-owned energy companies in the UK in 2015: Bristol Energy, which now has over 120,000 customers'[1].

To retain this leading role, Bristol needs to ensure a long term pipeline of sustainable energy projects, to ensure it remains on track to meeting its near term objectives, as well as ensuring the city becomes carbon neutral by 2050. The City Leap Programme [1] provides an urban living laboratory mechanism to demonstrate how to strategically manage such a wide ranging, diverse programme of works, as well as demonstrating the framing and catalytic role of local and central government.

The program aims to leverage over £1Bn of investment in low carbon energy projects (Figure 1). This includes substantial expansion of heat networks, the adoption and utilisation of smart energy systems, a massive increase in domestic and commercial energy efficiency, the expansion of renewable energy, green transport, hydrogen and marine energy opportunities as well as extensive monitoring, dissemination and evaluation.

Key Points

The opportunities and challenges for the developing this pipeline in the Bristol region were explored in two one hour 'world café' style workshop sessions. A summary of this discussion is provided below:

- 1. Specific resources.** Biomethane from surrounding pastoral agriculture was identified as a substantial untapped resource that is currently going to waste. Though there is a substantial resource in the Severn tidal estuary, continued ecological concerns of establishing a barrage frustrate energy developments. The question around the table was when should (if ever) low-carbon energy trump wildlife concerns. There is a desire to utilise the port and estuary for onshore wind also but no ties to residential green energy offers for citizens.

City Leap Programme at a glance	
Potential investment opportunity	Estimated investment opportunity over ten years
Heat networks	£300m
Smart energy system	£125m
Domestic energy efficiency	£300m
Commercial energy efficiency	£100m
Renewable energy	£40m
Monitoring, dissemination and evaluation	£10m
Transport	Additional
Hydrogen	Additional
Marine energy	Additional
Total	£875m

Figure 1 Bristol City Leap Investment Prospectus [1]

2. **Contradictory policy.** Much of the opportunities and pipeline of projects discussed were thought to require substantial buy in and local strategic action. The continued push to expand and improve the airport in the region runs counter to this and would undermine any net zero commitments.
3. **Business models currently unused.** There was seen to be a substantial opportunity for more local energy systems that operate under the 2.5MW derogation for supplier licensing for electricity provision particularly when linked with heat networks. However, this may mean operating with more than one supplier as some households already do, however, to ensure sufficient local take up and scale there may need to be a default to the local supplier when moving in and out of homes.

As with many such models the attractiveness of the offer depends on a volatile wholesale price which works against longer term investment and decarbonisation. Installation of PV on council domestic properties worked well under the FIT and some housing associations took advantage of this also. Without FIT these do not work or are very risky/marginal unless a better financing package is available and/or PV, more self or local consumption is possible, or PV is done as part of larger retrofit. The group also repeatedly referenced the whole house retrofit Energiesprong model as a positive approach but noted it was currently expensive until it could be done at scale.

4. **Opportunities facing known barriers** There is substantial commercial roof space in light commercial and medium scale manufacturing across the city region that is compatible with PV installation and also has predominantly daytime load. However previous citywide efforts to recruit this resource have largely failed due to most of this commercial space being owned by large non-local companies and leased to the occupants. This means citywide efforts are ineffective. While there is potential to find and approach the top commercial landlords in the area it is one level of remove away from local decision making.

There are 60+ large tower block type multi-residency buildings across Bristol with many more 4+ story multi-residency units. In these units there is a clear opportunity for rooftop solar to be shared between residences to offer a reliable daytime load for self-consumption. However, there is currently no know way in the city for each of these units to collectively self-consume this energy.

There is an opportunity to enshrine a minimum on site generation requirement in planning policy that is currently going through council. This is predominantly aimed at new build.

Business models

The traditional electricity business model relies on increasing throughput consumption of energy to generate profits. This has tended to create a monopoly position for a number of large multinational companies able to capture increasing economies of scale. The existential threat posed by climate change, alongside the proliferation and rapid cost reduction of smart, means distributed energy systems are presenting a direct challenge to this business model.

A recent body of research [2–4] identifies a range of new business models that could radically overhaul how energy is produced, delivered and consumed. Therefore, the diffusion of smart, distributed energy technologies such as rooftop solar, EVs and small-scale storage requires a more fundamental change to the incumbent business model.

Basic prosumer

The basic prosumer business model in the UK (Figure 2), typically involves distributed renewable electricity generation – usually wind or PV – installed behind the meter. Prosumers are able to benefit from the free electricity, provided they can self-consume at the moment of generation. When introduced in April 2010, the FIT scheme offered a generous £0.46/kWh for small rooftop solar installations and an export tariff of £0.0372-0.0524/kWh [5], for any energy they do not self-consume. The FIT has reduced through a process of ‘degression’, to a level of £0.0379 before the scheme’s closure on 31st March 2019, with the export tariff also coming to an end [4]. Figure 2 shows how the wider electricity system (upstream of licenced supplier) does not interact with this business model; with use of system charges, system operator functions such as the balancing mechanism and energy trading occurring without prosumer involvement.

Figure 2 Basic Prosumer Business Model

However, with the close out of the FIT and emerging disruptive technologies, this subsidy dependent business model has limited future potential in the UK. Despite significant cost reductions of PV panels, prosumers are increasingly unable to create economically-viable projects, in this post-subsidy landscape. Thus, new business models that improve export prices, promote increased self-consumption and access additional sources of revenue are increasingly seen as essential if the prosumer phenomenon is to have a future in the UK.¹

New business models

A range of new business models are being considered for distributed energy systems. These include the potential of energy service companies (ESCOs) to deliver useful services such as light, heat and useful work through long-term energy performance contracts [6–8]. Others emphasise how the diffusion of smart meters, internet of things (IoT)-enabled devices and blockchain technology may enable peer-to-peer (P2P) business models to become increasingly viable – potentially negating the need for traditional energy suppliers altogether [9,10]. Others explore how new business models based on electric mobility services may increasingly replace vehicle ownership [11,12] with others discussing how EVs can provide network services in vehicle to grid (V2G) models [13,14].

Others emphasise the trend towards local energy business models [2], where electricity is used close to its point of generation - promoting local value retention, energy democracy and justice [15]. Such outcomes are synonymous with resurgent forms of community [16] and municipal [17] energy governance, with increasing community and municipal ownership of renewable energy systems in countries such as the UK, Germany and the Netherlands [18].

The opportunities and challenges for the adoption of new business models were explored in two one hour ‘world café’ style workshop sessions. This included an initial ‘brainstorming session’, where the challenges and benefits of the following different business models was discussed and summarised overleaf:

- **Aggregator/ Virtual Power Plant**
- **Local Energy Market/Company**
- **Private Wire/Microgrids**
- **Corporate PPAs**
- **Energy Service Companies**

Subsequently, two business models were focused on in detail. The first was the private wire arrangement being trialled by Bristol Energy Coop at the Netham Weir hydroelectric site in Bristol. The second was the heat as a service business model being trialled by Bristol Energy. These two business models as well as the challenges they are facing are summarised on pages 10 and 11.

¹ ‘This text is taken from a forthcoming publication by the authors, currently under review [20]’

Bristol Energy Coop Hydro Private Wire

Scheme Description

- Netham Weir Hydroelectric Scheme
- Approx. 360W “Archimedes” screw
- Private wire arrangement with food storage warehouse

Scheme Business Model Issues

- Lack of FIT has degraded ROI to 1%
- Higher cost of capital from community energy investors >5% WACC
- Traditional debt investors view hydro as ‘high risk’
- Difficulty in selling project to developers without financing
- Uncertain long-term revenues from private wire client

Possible Solutions to Improve Business Case

- Secure lower cost of capital through public/hybrid finance
- Improved price for power/PPA with other buyers or local energy model?
- Reduce development risk and cost of development finance through partnering with council/developer

Bristol Energy-as-a-Service

Scheme Description

- Bristol Energy have launched a heat as a service business model
- Customers pay for internal temperature rather than units of fuel
- Shifts incentives onto supplier to ensure the heating system and home is as energy efficient as possible

Scheme Business Model Issues

- Currently model does not incentivize switching to low carbon heat such as heat pumps
- Difficulty in developing supply chain for energy efficiency measures
- Model could be enhanced through aggregation of flexibility of heat pump, batteries and solar PV towards creating a virtual power plant
- However, this would require some form of financing for the measures to be retrofitted into homes and some long-term repayment security through leasing/hire purchase agreements
- Aggregator capability also currently lacking

Possible Solutions to Improve Business Case

- Develop links with local energy efficiency supply chain, heat pump manufacturers and flexibility asset providers
- Develop in house capabilities in balancing mechanism, ancillary services and aggregation
- Develop financing mechanism for ESCO service provision through partnerships or special purpose vehicle

Finance

There is a clear gap between the volume of capital needed to enable low-carbon transitions, and the current level of investment. To meet climate change commitments, capital allocation to low-carbon investments must accelerate. As outlined by the City Leap prospectus in Bristol alone, these required investments are expected to exceed, £1Bn. Future projects must therefore leverage a range of different funding streams including the public, private and community sectors.

Dr Mark Davis lead researcher on the Financing for Society Project [10] presented findings of the report surrounding options for crowdfunding prosumer projects through an municipal bond using community investors (Figure 3):

Figure 3 Bristol City Council's "Community Municipal Bond" Option. Source: [10]

The challenges and opportunities for funding renewable energy projects were subsequently discussed in two one hour 'world café' style workshop sessions. The key themes from the discussion are summarised as follows:

- 1. Fixed Financial Returns are essential:** To bolster investment in RES prosumer initiatives, "sophisticated investors" (i.e. the 'serious money', as opposed to those who invest for a more blended return due to social / environmental motivations) demand a Fixed Financial Return. The 'serious money' is less likely to be persuaded by the "speculative value" of prosumer innovations and will leave these markets to those who 'believe' in them for other non-financial purposes. They are likely to need a target rate of around 4% before they would consider moving their money.

- 2. Renewables still ‘too risky’:** The discussion centred on Government-backed support for such innovative ventures (i.e. FIT subsidy) – without this, the post-subsidy landscape is deemed “too risky” for sophisticated investors. This point on risk was stressed by Jonathan Croley from Ashfords LLP, who suggested we looked into what happened with EIS (Enterprise Investment Scheme) and other Tax Breaks that had very mixed results from the investor point of view. We were also encouraged to look at the role of IFAs and the fiduciary duty of fund managers to maximise return to investors.
- 3. Who gets involved?** In the Bristol context, those approaching the investment community for funding were categorised as “sack cloths or suits” – i.e. there is an unsophisticated group who are seen to emerge from Bristol’s more liberal / alternative community energy scheme who ask you “to believe” in their projects; and there are sophisticated financial and legal professionals who offer you a clear value proposition based on financial returns based on “numbers”. Often getting the right intermediaries in place to broker trust between the two categories – and between these two categories and the public – is crucial (e.g. crowdfunding platforms).
- 4. Eco-system of Bristol** Prosumer initiatives need to understand the public perception of renewable energy investments, and play an active role in educating the public to understand the industry and to establish the reputation of the organisation that will be holding the money (i.e. their motivations, governance structure, outcomes delivered, stewarding of relationships / communications between state, market, and civil society, etc.). Bristol is somewhat unique as a living lab because there is a super-skilled eco-system in place with very knowledgeable private and public sector professionals working alongside local communities that are very well-informed and skilled in their own right with respect to climate action and progressive / alternative economies (e.g. Bristol Pound). The local authority and wider economic / industry partnerships have a suite of policy agendas that keep this eco-system healthy.
- 5. ‘Well-being funds’ don’t last** Because of the climate emergency, there is a certain leeway that is given to renewable energy initiatives that other sectors don’t enjoy (i.e. promise of social / environmental value outcomes). But this ‘well-being fund’ runs dry very quickly and people need to see that things are changing / benefitting them directly.
- 6. Case Study: Low Carbon Co-Op.** In considering ‘alternative finance’ options, Damon (?) encouraged us to look at a project in Manchester retrofitting homes for energy efficiencies. Initial financing mechanism was a £30k ‘gift’ per household to be spent on retrofit (which was rejected) followed by a proposal for a 0% loan over 30 years (which was adopted). Similar term to pension funds / debentures (i.e. debt-based crowdfunding model) but enabled the retrofitting to be undertaken immediately.

- 7. Shame, Shame, Shame.** In looking at behaviour change, shifting attitudes towards carbon and pressing the case for renewables needs to adopt the same strategy as the UK's smoking ban. "Tax the bad stuff" and stop advertising for carbon-intensive products and services. Shaming also needs to be enacted at the local / individual level – i.e. as with smoking, 'I' need to care about the impact of 'your' car driving / whatever on 'my' health, and so challenge you on it.

- 8. The Innovation Fetish.** Finally, there was widespread recognition on the table that the Government is wasting millions on innovation / enterprise grants that deliver nothing of any sustained value to anyone! There is a cultural obsession with 'innovative / disruptive start-ups' – i.e. again, a privileging of speculative value over empirical value – that is undermining attempts to build momentum for the climate emergency. Innovation funding would be better repurposed back into providing the FIT subsidy.

Regulation

One major barrier to the development of local energy markets is the current role of regulation. When the energy industry was privatised in the late 1980s, the market was designed with suppliers as the core intermediary between customers and the energy system, in what is known as the ‘supplier hub’ model. The current market arrangements have evolved and developed around this principle and the supplier’s role is now entrenched in legal frameworks, licensing arrangements, and industry codes, regulations and rules (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Current regulatory principles of UK energy markets. Source: [19]

However, a different market structure will be needed for an industry that transforms from a top-down system to one that fully enables distributed generation and peer-to-peer trading with a small amount of high voltage interconnection between distributed generation and smaller more localised networks.

The challenges and opportunities surrounding regulations and distributed renewable energy projects were subsequently discussed in two one hour ‘world café’ style workshop sessions. The key themes from the discussion are summarised as follows:

- 1. Need for regulatory principles to support prosumers:** Traditional market arrangements and regulatory frameworks were designed for an era of centralised suppliers operating in the ‘hub-and-spoke’ model. Some European countries now explicitly recognise the prosumer phenomenon in the design of their regulations, whilst there is an increasing move in this direction at EU level. Therefore, it was the view of the table that the UK and Ofgem should follow suit and explicitly recognise prosumers distinct role in the energy transition, set apart from grid connected distribution and transmission network generation.
- 2. Gap between technology and regulation:** there is consistently a gap between the progress of technology and the regulation that should accompany it. Particular examples include the development of internet of things enable devices and the standards of interoperability and

data protection. Initiatives such as Ofgem's regulatory sandbox provide promising opportunities, although these are not always widely exploited.

3. A related point is that the speed by which technological innovation is occurring, and the pace of change within regulatory agencies is fundamentally mismatched. This points to a broader issue around the relative inertia of civil service departments such as Ofgem and BEIS and perhaps point to the need for greater subsidiarity of regulation at the local authority or municipal level.
4. **Risk Aversion:** There may be reticence to introduce dynamic and innovative forms of regulation due to concerns surrounding vulnerable consumers. Whilst front runner consumers and actors may take up innovative government programs, become prosumers or adopt new technologies, the laggards should not be penalised. This is evident from the lack of consumer switching, programs such as the Supplier Obligation policies for energy efficiency, FITs and the subsequent impacts on consumer bills.
5. **Technology Neutrality:** Government has historically pursued an approach of not 'picking winners'. However, this approach is likely to become more problematic as key infrastructure decisions need to be made. Many city scale investments such as district heat and the move away from gas based heating will require strategic decisions that favour certain technological options ahead of others. This will also require a regulatory approach that is more specific to the needs of specific options.
6. **Uncertainty:** The aforementioned range of trajectories in key areas such as heat, transport and storage is creating confusion and hesitation in the development of new regulations for distributed energy systems. Examples such as distribution use of system charges for energy used close to the point of generation are a case in point, with little reward currently offered for local consumption.
7. **Regulation as a driver:** Regulation is often viewed as an impediment to the efficient operation of markets, however clear and stable regulation can set the direction of travel and allow the industry to invest in the future.
8. **National vs. Local:** As mentioned in several of the previous points there is a tension between the needs of the national and the local in energy system regulation. Greater subsidiary at city level/regional level would allow the specific context of the UK's regions and cities to be factored into the design of certain regulations. This approach is already the norm in the USA and also to a lesser extent in Germany.

Summary

Pipeline

- There are several clear opportunities to recruit commercial and multi residency buildings in collective self-consumption of small scale renewables in Bristol.
- There is no clear strategy of linking specific geographical resources such as agricultural biomethane, wind, or tidal to a citywide or neighbourhood scale self-consumption initiative.
- One clear next step for the research team would be to explore multi-residency self-consumption opportunities and business models.

Business models

The traditional prosumer business model, based on ‘dumb’ self-consumption behind the meter, poor prices for exported power and limited engagement with the wider energy system, is unlikely to be viable in the majority of cases. New business models can revenue streams in four key ways:

- Increase self-consumption
- Improved export prices
- Access flexibility, balancing and ancillary service markets
- Shift energy vectors

The challenge is to create business models which can capture these additional revenue streams, often requiring additional technical, regulatory and customer engagement capabilities, which were less important in the subsidy dominant era. Work needs to be done to develop this capacity through greater collaboration between key stakeholders in the city.

Finance

- New finance mechanisms are needed which blend the public sectors ability to underwrite lending and thus deliver a low cost of capital, with the large volumes of capital that exist in private savings
- Sophisticated institutional investors still view small scale renewables as high risk and may require fixed returns such as long term PPAs or FITs
- Better links need to be made between the traditional investment community and the green enthusiasts as projects become larger and more sophisticated.
- Initiatives also should continue to engage the public through encouraging them to invest as a ‘moral duty’ akin to public health campaigns around smoking – current London air pollution adverts are an example
- Government obsession with innovation is harming progress with viable, low cost solutions that are already developed. Energy efficiency is perhaps the most obvious, if ‘un-sexy’ example

Regulation

- Regulation should be designed to explicitly support prosumers, including incentivising them to use and trade energy locally through use of system and connection charges
- Regulators need to be bold and keep pace with the development and direction of technological change. This includes become less risk averse and more specific to the needs of different technologies and business models
- There is a need for greater localism and subsidiarity in the development of energy system regulation. Local authorities can and should be enabled to work more closely with regulators, DNOs and system operators to develop place specific regulation that is suitable at a region or city level

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